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GOOD GOVERNANCE AND CORRUPTION IN THE REGIONS

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ABSTRACT

The research objective is to determine the role of good governance as a preventive measure against corruption. The research method used is library research. Application of the principles of good governance, such as accountability, transparency, and the rule of law, may limit opportunities for corruption that efforts to combat crime more effectively. Tackling corruption must be implemented holistically with the participation of relevant parties, including those in government, the private sector, and the public, and by empowering preventive and repressive approaches. The research objective is to determine the role of good governance as a preventative measure against corruption. The research method used is library research.

KEYWORDS

Good Governance, Prevention of Corruption, Regions

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INTRODUCTION

The reform era and the regional autonomy policy, which massively decentralized the management of the bureaucratic apparatus to provincial governments, have not made public services in the regions better and of better quality, but on the contrary, that is, public services have become more complicated. One of the causes of this is the increasing number of corrupt behavior committed by state administrators. The practice of corruption, which was previously only carried out by high-ranking officials at the center, now has infected almost all regional officials (provincial, district, and city), both corruption carried out by officials and employees.

Regarding public bureaucratic services, conditions are worsening in the current reform era. This is marked by the handing over personnel management authority to staffing supervisors in each region. However, even more, frightening is when the personnel coaches are political officials who want direct political support to perpetuate political office. The modes used are mutations, large-scale promotions, and placement of someone's position that is not based on the ability and quality of the official. So what happens is the term like or dislike system can also lead to acts of abuse of power, which will give birth to acts of corruption.

[1] explains that in the era of regional autonomy, "little kings" were born, namely political officials as the highest leaders of the bureaucracy in the regions. So it is not surprising that in the current condition of our nation, there is a leadership crisis, an exemplary crisis, and increasingly massive acts of corruption occurring in the regions. The power that should be for service, what happens is to collect as many coffers of money and assets as possible by justifying any means. This phenomenon is most relevant to what was conveyed by DipoAlam in [2]) that from October 2004 to September 2012, there were 176 requests for permits to examine regional heads submitted by law enforcement to the president.

The most recent case is the arrest of the Regent of Banyuasin, South Sumatra, Yan Anton Ferdian, by the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) for allegedly accepting bribes (Ministry of Home Affairs: Low Anti-Corruption Mentality,

<http://www.koran-sindo.com/news.php?r=0&n=2&date=2016-09-06>).

Normatively, the practice of corruption is a reality of maladministration, in which the bureaucracy becomes uncontrollable, and in the end, it is difficult for bureaucratic organizations to measure their services. [3] categorizes corruption into three dimensions, namely: (a) corruption in the economic dimension stems from wrong symptoms in state management, where institutions designed to regulate relations between the state and the population are instead used to enrich themselves and gain additional profit for the corrupt; (b) corruption in the cultural dimension, in which case corruption is described as a tradition of giving bribes, gratuities, and other gifts; and (c) corruption in the political dimension, corruption is described as the corrupt behavior of actors in undergoing relations between the state and the private sector or between political actors and state institutions.

Even though many regulations and institutions have been established to eradicate corruption in the public service sector and other maladministration actions, corrupt acts and abuse of power are still commonly seen in society today.

Corruption is a social, economic, and political phenomenon; it can take various behavior patterns and forms in practice. Administrative officers can do corruption from the lower to the top levels. Corruption can also involve many parties, erode state finances, and undermine social and

religious foundations. Good governance is a reference for creating a better quality of government. The assumption built with good governance is that increasing the quality of good public services will reduce corruption and bring the government closer to fulfilling the community's interests [4].

Corruption as a phenomenon of deviation in social, cultural, social, and state life has been studied and critically examined by many scientists and philosophers. Aristotle, for example, who was followed by Machiavelli, formulated something he called moral corruption from the start. Moral corruption refers to various forms of the constitution that have been deviated so that the regime's rulers are included in the democratic system, are no longer led by law, and do not only try to serve themselves [5].

The research objective is to determine the role of good governance as a preventive measure against corruption.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Definition of Good Governance

"Government" or in English "governance," namely "the act, fact, manner of governing", means: "actions, facts, patterns, and activities or administration of government". Thus governance is an activity or process, as expressed by Kooiman in [6], that governance is more of a series of processes of socio-political interaction between government and society in various fields related to the interests of the community and government interference with these interests. While the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) states that (in Mardiasmo, 2010:17) good governance is "The exercise of political, economic, and administrative authority to manage a nation's affairs at all levels". Or if governance is interpreted, namely the emphasis on political (policy-making), economic (economic decision-making), and administrative (policy implementation systems) aspects in state management [7].

BintoroTjokroamidjojo quoted [8] views good governance as a form of development management, also referred to as development administration, which places the role of the central government as the agent of change in a developing society or developing in developing countries. Agent of transformation because the change he wants becomes planned change; that is why he is also called the Agent of Development.

The State Administration Institute concludes that good governance is the administration of a solid, responsible, efficient, and effective state government by maintaining the "synergy" of constructive interactions between state domains, the private sector, and society. In addition, Government Regulation Number 101 of 2000 defines the meaning of good governance as follows: governance that carries out will implement professionalism, accountability, transparency, excellent service, democracy, efficiency, effectiveness, and the rule of law and can be accepted by all people. According to [6] that the term good governance (good governance) contains an understanding of values that uphold the will or will of the people and values that can increase the ability of the people to achieve (national) goals of independence, sustainable development, and social justice.

B. Good Governance Principles

According to [9] that the principles of good governance consist of the following:

1. Participatory, every regulation or policy-making always involves community elements (through their representatives).

2. Rule of law, there must be a legal instrument that takes action against violators, guarantees the protection of human rights, is impartial, and applies to all citizens.
3. Transparency, there is the freedom to obtain public information for citizens who need it (regulated by law). There is a firmness between state secrets and state information that is open to the public.
4. Responsiveness, public institutions must be able to respond to the needs of society, especially those related to "basic needs" (basic needs) and human rights (civil rights, political rights, economic rights, social rights, and cultural rights).
5. Consensus, if there are fundamental differences in interests in society, the solution must prioritize the method of dialogue or deliberation to become a consensus.
6. Equal rights, the government must guarantee that all parties, without exception, are involved in the political process, without any party being sidelined.
7. Effectiveness and efficiency, the government must be effective and efficient in producing output through regulations, policies, management of state finances, etc.
8. Accountability is a manifestation of the obligation of a government agency to be accountable for the success and failure of the implementation of its mission.

C. Definition of Corruption

Corruption comes from the Latin word *Corruptio* or *Corruptus*. Then it appeared in English and French *Corruption*, in Dutch *Korruptie*, then in Indonesian it was called corruption. According to Sutarto, quoted by MansyurSemma, corruption refers to corrupt, rotten, dishonest actions associated with finances.

In the United Nations convention against corruption, the United Nation Convention Against Corruption, 2003 (UNCAC), which the Indonesian government has ratified with Law Number 7 of 2006, several acts are categorized as corruption [10], namely:

- a. Bribes, promises, offers or gifts to public or private officials, requests or acceptance by public or private or international officials, directly or indirectly, improper benefits for the officials themselves or other persons or entities intended to make the officials act or stop acting in the performance of their official duties to obtain help from such action.
- b. Embezzlement, abuse, or other irregularities by public/private/international officials.
- c. Enrich yourself illegally.

According to Law 31 of 1991, in conjunction with Law Number 20 of 2001 Article 2 that the definition of corruption is any person who unlawfully commits an act against himself or another person or a corporation that can harm state finances or the country's economy. Furthermore, in article 3, it is stated that every person who aims to benefit himself or another person or a corporation abuses the authority, opportunity or facilities available to him because of his position or position, which can be detrimental to state finances or the country's economy.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method is library research; data collection uses an approach based on the principles contained in laws and regulations, by including descriptions that are examined based on a literature review carried out carefully and in-depth.

Good governance's overall characteristics or principles are mutually reinforcing and interrelated and cannot stand alone. So if the implementation of good management or reasonable control in government organizations can be carried out according to what is supposed to be, this will automatically facilitate the implementation of activities in all fields.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Good Governance as a Solution

The concept of governance becomes very important and much discussed when the idea of government is considered less capable of being a leader in keeping up with rapid changes in the realm of public services. The difference in question is the increasing complexity of governance. In the current government administration, external parties who can support the government's performance to create better public services are needed.

Three things make governance a concept that needs to be developed: (1) governance is an administrative system involving many actors from the government and non-governmental elements. Governance is not a substitute for government but rather a complement to a government. Policies are no longer developed by solely considering formal legal and constitutional aspects but also considering factors of values that form in society; (2) Governance or government is deliberately designed to respond to problems and public interests. The concentration of governance is on the collective public interest and not on the interests of individual citizens; and (3) The structure developed is not a formal, rigid, and rigid structure but an informal, flexible, and loose structure. Governance is a mechanism for managing economic and social resources that involves the influence of the state sector and the non-government sector in a collective activity. Pinto was quoted [11] as saying that governance is the practice of administering power and authority by the government in managing government affairs in general and economic development in particular.

Governance is the process of administering state power in carrying out the provision of public goods and services. Governance can be reviewed from whether the government has functioned effectively and efficiently to achieve the goals outlined or vice versa [12]. Governance is defined as exercising political, economic, and administrative authority to manage the affairs of the nation and state [13].

To achieve the goals of ideal governance, three things must be completed: (1) Economic governance, which includes the decision-making process that affects the country's economic activity or relates to other economies either directly or indirectly. Therefore, economic governance has influence or implications for equity, poverty, and quality of life. (2) political governance refers to the process of making decisions and implementing policies of a state that are legitimate and authoritative. Because of this, the state should consist of three separate branches of government, namely the executive, legislative, and judiciary, which can represent pluralist political interests; and (3) Administrative governance, namely the policy implementation system that implements the public sector in an efficient, impartial, accountable and open manner. Governance applies and takes place at all levels, both national and local.

Meanwhile, good governance is understood as fulfilling the principles of accountability, transparency, responsiveness, equality and justice, effectiveness and efficiency, legal certainty, participation, and representation.

B. Implementation in Indonesia

The spirit of reform that began in 1998 became an important milestone in the life of Indonesian democracy. In addition to replacing the authoritarian regime, the reform movement also voiced eradicating corruption, collusion, and nepotism (KKN). During 16 years, the struggle to eliminate corruption, collusion, and nepotism through bureaucratic reform has not achieved maximum results, so the achievement of good governance has not been able to fulfill the desire of the initial struggle for reform.

The measurement parameter of the lack of maximum performance in realizing good governance cannot be separated from the unprofessional performance of the bureaucracy and rampant corruption cases. In addition, [14] sees that the bureaucracy in Indonesia is still irrational, fat (rich in structure, poor in function), not neutral, and not transparent. In addition, implementing good governance in Indonesia is still not optimal and tends to stagnate because our bureaucrats have not been able to separate political positions from bureaucratic positions [15].

The realization of good governance in Indonesia cannot be separated from the success or failure of bureaucratic performance. Both have a positive relationship in the sense of mutual influence. Better and more intensive performance of the bureaucracy and community empowerment will positively affect the development of the nation and state.

A synergistic relationship between the government and the community will result in a strong government supported by the community. It takes courage to make changes or reform the bureaucracy to realize better governance services. The strategy undertaken can be started with the recruitment process of professional human resources. The bureaucracy must conduct a fit and proper test to avoid collusion and nepotism. The bureaucracy needs to provide rewards and salary rewards by achievement (reward merit system), not deceitful, discriminatory, and less educational (spoil system) work relationships; it is also essential to put forward a pattern of reward and punishment which may not have worked so far. The government bureaucracy must be neutral and able to distinguish between public and political positions so that it does not take advantage of state facilities for personal, group, group, or political party interests. Another strategy to fix the bureaucracy includes the following four important aspects: First, preparation of the legal framework for bureaucratic management by making changes to the personnel law. Second, the bureaucracy must be managed professionally and not tied to a political party. Third, the placement of employee positions that are adjusted to the potential or technical abilities of each. Fourth, there must be a prohibition against the politicization of the bureaucracy by political officials both at the center and in the regions [15].

CONCLUSION

Building a bureaucratic culture in an ideal government system is making the attitudes and behavior of the system that the perpetrators must follow consistently to create excellent and trustworthy governance. Answering the nation's current problems regarding the chaotic bureaucratic system, increasingly massive acts of corruption, which have become the culture of Indonesian society, have failed to realize good governance in the community.

The criminal act of corruption based on abuse of authority is essentially an act of maladministration in administrative law. To avoid criminal acts of corruption in the form of abuse of power, it is necessary to have the principle of good governance.

To answer all the problems that are being faced and the desire to realize the national goal of a sovereign, prosperous Indonesian nation, there must be courage or political will from all parties to want to learn and implement the existing regulations consistently. In addition, there must also be concrete action in efforts to reform the bureaucracy to realize a clean and accountable government (good governance). To learn good power, the proposal is realistic and must be followed up by all parties, the community, and the leaders.

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